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BURNOUT SYNDROME IN TEACHERS: THE SILENT WEAR AND TEAR OF AN "IMPOSSIBLE" PROFESSION

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ABSTRACT

Teachers' mental health has become a topic of increasing scientific relevance, given the high levels of stress present in teaching practice. Burnout Syndrome, also known as Professional Exhaustion Syndrome, is characterized by physical and emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and low professional accomplishment, being especially frequent among professionals who deal intensively with people, such as those in education. The concept was further developed by Christina Maslach and Suzan Jackson, based on the pioneering studies of Freudenberger (1974). In the school context, teachers face overcrowded classrooms, emotional pressures, repetitive tasks, and the challenge of playing multiple roles, which makes them highly vulnerable to burnout. The lack of emotional rewards in the profession contributes to a growing sense of frustration and helplessness. Therefore, it is urgent to discuss strategies for valuing and caring for teachers, preventing the effects of the syndrome on their health and on the quality of education.

Keywords: Burnout. Teachers. Stress.